

TEKNIK OLIY TA'LIM TALABALARINING MATEMATIK QOBILIYATINI OPERATSION HISOB MASALALARI YECHISH ORQALI OSHIRISH

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada texnik yoʻnalishdagi oliy taʼlim talabalarining qobiliyatlarini operatsion hisobning masalarini yechish orqali oshirish usullari koʻrsatilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: matematik-fizika, operatsion hisob, Laplas almashtirishi, original, tasvir, uzluksiz funksiya, xususiy hosilalar.

Hozirgi kunda har bir sohada juda koʻp izlanishlar va bu yoʻnalishlarda oʻziga hos yutuqlarga erishib kelinmoqda. Bu yutuqlarga erishish uchun ushbu sohani yaxshi bilgan holda yondashish zarur hisoblanmoqda. Texnika sohasida tehsil olayotgan talabalar ham oʻz bilimlarini amaliyotga qoʻllashda ularni nazariy bilimlari muhimdir. Jumladan, matematikadagi bilim va qobiliyatlarini oshirishda shu fanga xos boʻlgan masalalarni yechishdan va tushunishdan iboratdir. Matematik-fizikaning ayrim murakkab masalalarini yechishda qiyinchilikarga duch kelamiz. Bunday hollarda operatsion hisob masalalarini yechish oson tenglamalarini yechish oson tenglamalarni yechishga olib keladi. Ushbu murakkab masalalarning tenglamalari Laplas almashtirishlari orqali tasvirga oʻtiladi, soʻngra yechimi topiladi. Soʻngra bu yechim yana originalga oʻtkaziladi. Buning uchun maxsus original va tasvirlar jadvalidan foydalaniladi, hamda izlangan yechim topiladi.

Bu maqolada matematik- fizikaning asosiy tenglamalari hisoblangan toʻlqin va issiqlik oʻtkazish tenglamalari orqali yechiladigan baʼzi bir masalalarni yechishni qarab chiqamiz.

Faraz qilaylik, izlanayotgan funksiya ikki oʻzgaruvchi x va z ga bogʻliq boʻlsin, bu yerda t – fazoviy koordinata, x – vaqtni bildiradi. Qaralayotgan nostatsionar

masala albatta boshlang‘ich shartlarga bog‘liq, ya’ni fizik jarayonga o‘tishga bog‘liq deb olib uni yechimini izlaymiz.

Aytaylik, hususiy hosilali differensial tenglama quyidagi ko‘rinishga ega bo‘lsin:

$$A \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + B \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + Cu + A_1 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} + B_1 \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = 0, \quad (1)$$

bu yerda A, B, C, A_1, B_1 – x ning uzluksiz funksiyalari bo‘lib, $0 \leq x \leq l$ kesmada berilgan, $A > 0$ deb olish mumkin.

Asosiy ikki narsaga ahamiyat beramiz:

- 1) agar $A_1 < 0$ bo‘lsa, berilgan tenglama giperbolik tipda bo‘ladi;
- 2) agar $A_1 = 0, B_1 < 0$ bo‘lsa, berilgan tenglama parabolik tipda bo‘ladi;

Bu shartlarga tayanib, qo‘yilgan nostatsionar masalani quyidagicha qo‘yish mumkin: (1) tenglamani $0 \leq x \leq l$ oraliqda $t \geq 0$ bo‘lgandagi $u(x, t)$ yechimini topishda

$$u(x, t) \Big|_{t=0} = \varphi(x), \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} \Big|_{t=0} = \psi(x) \quad (A_1 < 0 \text{ bo‘lganda}) \quad (2)$$

boshlang‘ich shartlar va

$$u(x, t) \Big|_{x=0} = f(t), \quad \alpha \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=l} + \beta \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} \Big|_{x=l} = \gamma u(x, t) \Big|_{x=l} \quad (3)$$

chegaraviy shartlardan foydalanish kerak bo‘ladi, bunda α, β, γ – o‘zgarmaslar, $l \rightarrow \infty$ da chegaraviy shartlarning ikkinchisi o‘z-o‘zidan qo‘llanilmaydi.

Masalani yechish jarayonida t o‘zgaruvchiga bog‘liq bo‘lgan funksiya va uning birinchi, ikkinchi tartibli hususiy hosilalari original bo‘lib xizmat qilishi va tasvirlar orqali ifodalanishi mumkin bo‘lsa, uni quyidagicha yozish mumkin:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \bar{u}(x, p) &= \int_0^\infty e^{-pt} u(x, t) dt, \\ \frac{d\bar{u}}{dx} &= \int_0^\infty e^{-pt} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} dt = \frac{d}{dx} \int_0^\infty u e^{-pt} dt, \\ \frac{d^2 \bar{u}}{dx^2} &= \int_0^\infty e^{-pt} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} dt = \frac{d^2}{dx^2} \int_0^\infty u e^{-pt} dt \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (4)$$

bu yerda p – parametr.

Hosilalarning tasviri

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} \leftarrow p\bar{u} - \varphi(x), \quad \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} \leftarrow p^2 \bar{u} - p\varphi(x) - \psi(x);$$

$$\bar{u} \Big|_{x=0} = \bar{f}(p), \left[\alpha \frac{d\bar{u}}{dx} + \beta(p\bar{u} - \varphi(x)) \right]_{x=l} = \gamma \bar{u} \Big|_{x=l}$$

Shunday qilib, (1) tenglamani yechish

$$A \frac{d^2 \bar{u}}{dx^2} + B \frac{d\bar{u}}{dx} + M\bar{u} + N = 0 \quad (5)$$

ko‘rinishdagi 2-tartibli oddiy differensial tenglamani yechishga keltiriladi, bu yerda $M = C - A_1 p^2 + B_1 p$, $N = A_1 p \varphi - A_1 \varphi - B_1 \varphi$

$u(x, t)$ ni tasvirini bilgan holda originalga qaytamiz.

Misol. $u(x, 0) = A \sin\left(\frac{n\pi x}{l}\right)$, $0 \leq x \leq l$ boshlang‘ich va $0 \leq x \leq l$,

$u(0, t) = u(l, t) = 0$ chegaraviy shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi $\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} = \alpha^2 \frac{\partial u}{\partial t}$

issiqlik o‘tkazish tenglamasini yechimini toping.

Yechish. Operator tenglamani tuzamiz:

$$\frac{d^2 \bar{u}}{dx^2} - \alpha^2 p \cdot \bar{u} = -\alpha^2 A \sin \frac{n\pi x}{l}$$

Bu tenglamani umumiy yechimi

$$\bar{u}(x, p) = C_1 e^{-\alpha \sqrt{p} x} + C_2 e^{\alpha \sqrt{p} x} + \frac{A}{p + \frac{n^2 \pi^2}{\alpha^2 l^2}} \sin \frac{n\pi x}{l} \text{ bo‘ladi.}$$

$\bar{u} \Big|_{x=0} = \bar{u} \Big|_{x=l} = 0$ chegaraviy shartlarni qo‘llab,

$\bar{u}(x, p) = \frac{A}{p + \frac{n^2 \pi^2}{\alpha^2 l^2}} \sin \frac{n\pi x}{l}$ tenglamani original yechimini topamiz:

$$u(x, t) = A \frac{n^2 \pi^2 t}{\alpha^2 l^2} \cdot \sin \frac{n\pi x}{l};$$

Bu maqoladan xulosa qilib shuni aytish mumkin, operatsion hisob oliy matematikaning juda muhim bo‘limi bo‘lib, ba’zi bir differensial va integral tenglamalarni yechishda keng qo‘llaniladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

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